

Time-Varying Statistics of Oscillators Endowed with Fractional Derivative Elements

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ABSTRACT: An approximate technique is presented for determining the statistics of the response envelope of lightly-damped nonlinear oscillators endowed with fractional derivative elements. Specifically, via the stochastic averaging concept, a one-dimensional first order stochastic differential equation governing the response envelope of the oscillator, and the corresponding Fokker-Planck-Kolmogorov equation are obtained. Next, an analytical solution of the linear systems is considered, and the nonlinear oscillator solution is sought by a Galerkin scheme with base functions selected as the eigenfunctions associated with the solution of the linear oscillator. As an example, a Van der Pol oscillator endowed with fractional derivative elements subject to Gaussian white noise is examined. Comparisons with pertinent Monte Carlo simulation results are made to demonstrate the reliability of the proposed technique.

Fractional calculus has successfully been used in various field of mechanics and engineering in recent decades (Kilbas et al. (2006), Machado et al. (2011)). Stochastic responses of oscillators endowed with fractional derivative elements have been extensively studied. Initial analytical solutions for linear systems endowed with fractional derivative elements can be found in references such as Spanos and Zeldin (1997), Agrawal (2001), and further investigations and studies are also available in Huang et al. (2010), Di Paola et al. (2012), and Kazem (2013). However, the multiple integration form of the analytical solutions has made the computation extremely cumbersome even for one dimensional and single degree of freedom (SDOF) systems. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no exact analytical solution for any nonlinear system endowed with fractional derivative elements has been obtained.

Naturally, several numerical schemes were developed for effectively solving the fractional differential equations even for the multi-

dimensional ones (Yuan and Agrawal (2002), Spanos and Evangelatos (2010), Failla and Pirrotta (2012), Su and Xian (2022)), which can be further combined with other sample based numerical methods for seeking the response statistics of fractional differential oscillators.

Besides the exact analytical solutions and the purely numerical ones, many approximate analytical and semi-analytical techniques were developed for determining the statistics of linear and nonlinear fractional differential oscillators. For example, statistical linearization (Spanos and Evangelatos (2010), Kong et al. (2022, a), Spanos and Zhang (2022)), harmonic wavelets (Kougioumtzoglou and Spanos (2016), Dos Santos et al. (2020), Kong and Spanos (2020), Kong et al. (2022, b)), stochastic perturbation (Xu et al. (2016)), Wiener Path integral (Di Matteo et al. (2014)), and globally-evolving-based generalized density evolution equation (GE-GDEE) (Luo et al. (2022, 2023)), etc. Among all these methods, the stochastic averaging is rather extensively employed (Huang

and Jin (2009), Chen et al. (2011), Li et al. (2015), Spanos et al. (2016, 2018), Di Matteo et al. (2018), Fragkoulis et al. (2019), Jiang and Li (2019), Zhang et al. (2021)). Note that a scheme for determining the response statistics via stochastic averaging is to apply statistical linearization (refer to Fragkoulis et al. (2019), Zhang et al. (2021), Kougioumtzoglou et al. (2022)), and to approximate the response envelope distribution by a Rayleigh distribution. To circumvent the limitation of such approximation, in this paper, a Galerkin scheme is employed to determine the probability density function (PDF) of the response envelope.

Specifically, based on the stochastic averaging concept, an approximate technique is presented for determining the statistics of the response envelope of lightly-damped oscillators endowed with fractional derivative elements. For this purpose, an approximation for the fractional derivative, broadly used in the literature, is adopted, yielding an equivalent integer-order differential system. Further, the stochastic differential equation governing the response envelope of the oscillator, and the corresponding Fokker-Planck-Kolmogorov (FPK) equation are obtained. Thereby, the approximate analytical solution of linear systems can be readily given as a Rayleigh distribution. For nonlinear systems, a Galerkin scheme with base functions the eigenfunctions of the solution of the linear oscillators is employed to obtain the PDF solution and the statistical moments in an efficient manner. A Van der Pol oscillator endowed with fractional derivative elements subject to Gaussian white noise is studied to assess the reliability of the proposed technique.

1. FORMULATION

Consider an SDOF oscillator with fractional derivative elements subject to a random excitation governed by the equation

$$\ddot{X}(t) + 2\zeta\omega_0\dot{X}(t) + \omega_0^2 X(t) + C_\alpha \mathcal{D}^\alpha X(t) + Z(X(t), \dot{X}(t), t) = f(t), \quad (1)$$

where $X(t)$, $\dot{X}(t)$, and $\ddot{X}(t)$ relatively denote the displacement, velocity, and acceleration of the oscillator; ζ_0 and ω_0 relatively denote the linear damping ratio and natural frequency; C_α is a constant; $Z(X(t), \dot{X}(t), t)$ is a deterministic nonlinear function with respect to $X(t)$, $\dot{X}(t)$, and t ; $f(t)$ is a Gaussian, zero-mean broad-band process with evolutionary power spectrum $S(\omega, t)$; and $\mathcal{D}^\alpha X(t)$ denotes the Caputo fractional derivative defined as

$$\mathcal{D}^\alpha X(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{\dot{X}(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^\alpha} d\tau, \quad 0 \leq \alpha < 1. \quad (2)$$

Next, resorting to the stochastic averaging procedure, the response envelope or amplitude $A(t)$, and the phase $\theta(t)$ are introduced by the equations

$$X(t) = A(t) \cos(\omega(A)t + \theta(t)), \quad (3)$$

and

$$\dot{X}(t) = -A(t)\omega(A)\sin[\omega(A)t + \theta(t)], \quad (4)$$

where $\omega(A)$ is the equivalent natural frequency dependent on $A(t)$. Therefore, it can be readily found that

$$A(t) = \left[X^2(t) + \frac{\dot{X}^2(t)}{\omega^2(A)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\theta(t) = -\tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\dot{X}}{\omega X}\right) - \omega t \quad (6)$$

Differentiating Eq. (5) yields

$$\dot{A}(t) = \frac{1}{A(t)} \left[X(t)\dot{X}(t) + \frac{\dot{X}(t)\ddot{X}(t)}{\omega^2(A)} \right] \quad (7)$$

Denote $\omega(A)$ as ω , and $\psi = \omega t + \theta(t)$, for short. Further, introduce the approximation of the fractional derivative term as in Li et al. (2015), Spanos et al. (2016, 2018), Di Matteo (2018), and Fragkoulis (2019), that is,

$$\mathcal{D}^\alpha X(t) \approx \omega^{\alpha-1} \left[\dot{X} \sin \frac{\pi\alpha}{2} + \omega X \cos \frac{\pi\alpha}{2} \right] + O(t)^{-\alpha}. \quad (8)$$

As $t \rightarrow \infty$, the term $O(t)^{-\alpha}$ in Eq. (8) diminishes.

Then, based on the stochastic averaging procedure, one may obtain the following governing equation of $A(t)$

$$\dot{A}(t) = F(A) + \frac{\pi S}{2A\omega^2} - \zeta\omega A + \frac{\sqrt{\pi S}}{\omega} \xi(t), \quad (9)$$

where

$$F(A) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -\frac{\dot{x}}{A\omega^2} Z(x, \dot{x}, t) d\psi \quad (10)$$

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\int_0^{2\pi} Z(x, \dot{x}) x d\psi}{\int_0^{2\pi} x^2 d\psi} + C_\alpha \omega^\alpha \cos \frac{\pi\alpha}{2} + \omega_0^2, \quad (11)$$

and

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{\omega} \left(\zeta_0 \omega_0 + \frac{1}{2} C_\alpha \omega^{\alpha-1} \sin \frac{\pi\alpha}{2} \right). \quad (12)$$

Note that Eq. (9) is obtained based on the assumptions

$$\zeta = \frac{c_e}{2\omega} \ll 1, \quad (13)$$

and

$$S(\omega, t) = O(\zeta). \quad (14)$$

The FPK equation associated with Eq.(9) is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = & \frac{\partial}{\partial A} \left[\left(F(A) + \zeta\omega A - \frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{2A\omega^2} \right) p \right] \\ & + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial}{\partial A} \left[\frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{\omega^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial A} + \frac{\partial}{\partial A} \left(\frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{\omega^2} p \right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

with boundary $0 \leq A(t) < \infty$, and boundary condition

$$\lim_{A \rightarrow \infty} p(A, t) = 0. \quad (16)$$

Note that for linear and Van der Pol kind of oscillators, the first term in the right hand side of Eq. (11) vanishes, that is,

$$\omega^2 = C_\alpha \omega^\alpha \cos \frac{\pi\alpha}{2} + \omega_0^2. \quad (17)$$

Then, Eq. (11) becomes an algebraic equation with respect to ω which can be easily solve. This means that for the systems considered in this work, ω and ζ can be determined independently of $A(t)$. Thus, the excitation term in Eq. (9) becomes additive, and the FPK equation (Eq. (15)) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial A} \left[\left(F(A) + \zeta\omega A - \frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{2A\omega^2} \right) p \right] + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{\omega^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial A^2}, \quad (18)$$

An approximate solution of the probability density function (PDF) of the amplitude $A(t)$ corresponding to a linear integer-order differential system can be given as

$$p_L(A, t) = \frac{A}{\tilde{\sigma}_s^2 s(t)} \exp\left(-\frac{A^2}{2\tilde{\sigma}_s^2 s(t)}\right), \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_s^2 = \frac{\pi S_0}{2\zeta\omega^3}$, and $S_0 = \max[S(\omega, t)]$, and

$$s(t) = \frac{(2\zeta\omega)}{S_0} \exp(-2\zeta\omega t) \int_0^t \exp(2\zeta\omega\tau) S(\omega, \tau) d\tau. \quad (20)$$

2. GALERKIN SCHEME FOR NONLINEAR CASES

The FPK equation of the envelope of nonlinear oscillators endower with fractional derivatives is treated via a Galerkin scheme based on the series expansion in terms of the eigenfunctions of linear system, as proposed and employed in [Spanos \(1976, 1978\)](#), [Spanos et al. \(2007\)](#). Several analytical recursive formulas for the computations associated with the eigenfunctions have been proposed to significantly reduce the computational cost for solving the FPK equation, as detailed illustrated in [Spanos \(1976\)](#) and [Spanos et al. \(2007\)](#). On this basis, and to minimize the numerical integration involved, the PDF solution is expressed as

$$p(A, t) = p_L(A, t) + \sum_{r=0}^N c_r(t) B_r(A), \quad (21)$$

where $p_L(A, t)$ accounts for the solution of the linear oscillator by setting the $Z(X(t), \dot{X}(t), t)$ in Eq. (1) as zero; $N \geq 0$ is an integer; $c_r(t)$ are time-varying parameters to be determined; and $B_r(A)$ are the eigenfunctions given by

$$B_r(A) = \frac{1}{r!} \frac{A}{\tilde{\sigma}_s^2} \exp\left[-\frac{A^2}{2\tilde{\sigma}_s^2}\right] L_r\left[\frac{A^2}{2\tilde{\sigma}_s^2}\right], \quad (22)$$

and $L_r(\cdot)$ denotes the Laguerre polynomial defined as

$$L_n(x) = e^x \frac{d^n}{dx^n} (e^{-x} x^n). \quad (23)$$

The following properties regarding $B_r(A)$ have been readily proved (Spanos et al. (2007)):

$$(1) \quad \int_0^\infty \frac{B_k(A)B_r(A)}{B_0(A)} dA = \delta_{kr}, \quad (24)$$

where δ_{kr} is the Kronecker delta symbol.

$$(2) \quad (r+1)B_{r+1}(A) = \left(2r+1 - \frac{A^2}{2\tilde{\sigma}_s^2}\right)B_r(A) - rB_{r-1}(A). \quad (25)$$

$$(3) \quad \frac{dB_r(A)}{dA} = \frac{1}{A} \left[2(r+1)B_{r+1}(A) - (2r+1)B_r(A)\right]. \quad (26)$$

$$(4) \quad I_{n+2,r,k} = 2\tilde{\sigma}_s^2 \left[(2k+1)I_{n,r,k} - kI_{n,r,k-1} - (k+1)I_{n,r,k+1}\right], \quad (27)$$

where $I_{n,r,k} = \int_0^\infty A^n \frac{B_r(A)B_k(A)}{B_0(A)} dA$, and $I_{0,r,k} = \delta_{rk}$.

$$(5) \quad I_{n,r+1} = \frac{r-n/2}{r+1} I_{n,r}, \quad (28)$$

where $I_{n,r} = \int_0^\infty A^n B_r(A) dA$. When n is even,

$$I_{n,r} = 0 \text{ for } r > \frac{n}{2}.$$

Rewrite the FPK equation (Eq. (18)) as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial L} = \mathcal{L}_L(p) + \mathcal{L}_{NL}(p), \quad (29)$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_L(p) = \frac{\partial}{\partial A} \left[\left(\zeta \omega A - \frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{2A\omega^2} \right) p \right] + \frac{\pi S(\omega, t)}{2\omega^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial A^2}, \quad (30)$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}_{NL}(p) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial A} [F(A)p]. \quad (31)$$

Substituting Eq. (21) into Eq. (29), the residual error can be derived as

$$R[A, c_r(t)] = \sum_{r=0}^N \dot{c}_r(t) B_r(A) - \mathcal{L}_L \left[\sum_{r=0}^N c_r(t) B_r(A) \right] - \mathcal{L}_{NL} [p_L(A, t)] - \mathcal{L}_{NL} \left[\sum_{r=0}^N c_r(t) B_r(A) \right], \quad (32)$$

where the following formula has been proved

$$\mathcal{L}_L \left(\sum_{r=0}^N c_r(t) B_r(A) \right) = -\sum_{r=0}^N \lambda_r c_r(t) B_r(A), \quad (33)$$

in which $\lambda_r = 2\zeta\omega r$ denote the eigen values.

Taking $B_k(A)/B_0(A)$ as the weighting function of the Galerkin scheme, one has

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{B_k(A)}{B_0(A)} R[A, c_r(t)] dA = 0. \quad (34)$$

Substituting Eq. (32), Eq. (24) and Eq. (33) into Eq. (34), the following ordinary differential equation governing $\mathbf{c}(t) = [c_0(t), c_1(t), \dots, c_N(t)]^T$ is obtained (Spanos et al. (2007))

$$\dot{\mathbf{c}}(t) = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{c}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t), \quad (35)$$

where

$$D_{kr} = -\lambda_k \delta_{kr} + \int_0^\infty \frac{B_k(A)}{B_0(A)} \mathcal{L}_{NL} [B_r(A)] dA, \quad (36)$$

and

$$F_k(t) = \int_0^\infty \frac{B_k(A)}{B_0(A)} \mathcal{L}_{NL} [p_L(A, t)] dA. \quad (37)$$

To further reduce the computational effort, $p_L(A, t)$ is approximated as (Spanos and Lutes (1980))

$$p_L(A, t) \approx \sum_{r=0}^N B_r(A) [u(t)]^r, \quad (38)$$

where $u(t) = 1 - s(t)$. Then Eq. (37) can be further recast as

$$F_k(t) = \sum_{r=0}^N [u(t)]^r \int_0^\infty \frac{B_k(A)}{B_0(A)} \mathcal{L}_{NL} [B_r(A)] dA. \quad (39)$$

Finally, the moments $m_{L,j}(t) = \int_0^\infty A^j p_L(A, t) dA$ can be expressed as

$$m_j(t) = E[a^j(t)] = m_{L,j}(t) + \sum_{r=0}^N c_r(t) I_{j,r}. \quad (40)$$

Eq. (40) can be implemented efficiently using Eq. (28).

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE: VAN DER POL OSCILLATOR

In this section, a Van der Pol oscillator endowed with fractional derivative elements is studied. The equation of motion is given by Eq. (1) with

$$Z(x, \dot{x}, t) = 2\zeta_0\omega_0 \left(-\dot{x} + \frac{\varepsilon}{\sigma_s^2} x^2 \dot{x} \right). \quad (41)$$

The excitations $f(t)$ is taken as a stationary Gaussian white noise with $S(\omega, t) = S_0$. Thus, Eq. (20) can be expressed by

$$s(t) = 1 - \exp(-2\zeta\omega t). \quad (42)$$

Further, Eq. (10) can be cast as

$$F(A) = 2\zeta_0\omega_0 A - \frac{\varepsilon \zeta_0\omega_0}{4 \sigma_s^2} A^3. \quad (43)$$

Thus, Eq. (31) becomes

$$\mathcal{L}_{NL}(p) = -2\zeta_0\omega_0 \frac{\partial(Ap)}{\partial A} + \frac{\varepsilon \zeta_0\omega_0}{4 \sigma_s^2} \frac{\partial(A^3 p)}{\partial A}, \quad (44)$$

and the integral in Eq. (36) and Eq. (39) can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^\infty \frac{B_k(A)}{B_0(A)} \mathcal{L}_{NL}[B_r(A)] dA \\ &= -2\zeta_0\omega_0 [2(r+1)\delta_{k,r+1} - 2r\delta_{k,r}] \\ & \quad + \frac{\varepsilon \zeta_0\omega_0}{4 \sigma_s^2} [2(r+1)I_{2,k,r+1} - 2(r-1)I_{2,k,r}] \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

The parameters can be computed using the recursive formula in Eq. (27). Thus, in the implementation of Eq. (35), no numerical integration is required.

The system parameters considered in the numerical example are $\omega_0 = 1$, $\zeta_0 = 0.01$, $C_\alpha = 0.5$, $\alpha = 0.1$, $\varepsilon = 2$, and $2\pi S_0 = 0.2$. 20 terms in Eq. (21), that is, $N = 19$ is used for the approximation. Results obtained by the proposed method are compared with pertinent Monte Carlo simulation with 10000 samples. The first two moments calculated by Eq. (40) are shown in Figure 1. Results regarding the PDFs at several time instants are shown in Figure 2. Quite good agreements can be observed, which demonstrate the reliability of the proposed scheme.

Figure 1: Comparison of the first two moments with the MCS results

Figure 2: Comparison of the PDFs obtained by the proposed scheme and MCS at various time instants.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper the stochastic averaging concept has been employed to determine the time-varying amplitude moments, and PDFs of randomly excited nonlinear oscillators endowed with fractional derivative elements. By using a reliable approximation of the fractional derivative, the original fractional differential system has been replaced by an integer-order differential one. Then the governing equation of motion and the FPK equation corresponding to the response envelop of the oscillator have been obtained. For this purpose, a Galerkin scheme has been employed to solve the FPK equation of nonlinear system. Using the eigenfunctions of the corresponding linear system as the base functions, the solution has been obtained in a quite efficient manner. A Van der Pol oscillator

endowed with fractional derivative element subject to stationary Gaussian white noise has been investigated to assess the validity and accuracy of the proposed scheme. Obviously, the proposed scheme is expected to be applicable to other nonlinear fractional differential systems subject to nonstationary excitations.

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